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Are Teachers Born Leaders or Made?

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For the longest time, it is my understanding that leaders are born meaning that there are those who are born with the ability to lead others. But later on, I realized, based on what I have seen and experienced, that leaders are made. Anyone has the potential to become a leader and that we only have to discover the leader in us.

There were so many times in the past that I avoided to take assignments of leadership because of fear and uncertainty. I was less sure if I can do justice to the position or job. Most of the time, I opted to be a follower for I felt that I was not a leader.

It took my job as a teacher to make me realize that leaders are made. It can be developed. Skills can be acquired and practiced. Leadership has nothing to do with personality. You just have to leave your comfort zone and learn to understand social situations and processes, and choose the right action at the right time. Just like anything else, you can achieve anything you set your heart to through hard work.

It is my childhood dream to become a teacher and this drove me to pursue a vocation in education. Later, I realized that teaching my students also entails being an inspiration to them to be the best they can be. Someone said, "The mediocre teacher tells, the good teacher explains, the superior teacher demonstrates, the great teacher inspires," I want to be a great teacher! To do this, I need to set an example for my students to follow which requires leadership. At first, I sort of drifted into the position because I have no choice but over time, as I was assigned leadership positions at school other than teaching, this helps developed skills and abilities that I did not know I have. The position prepared me to be more accepting of my leadership role in the lives of my students. Leadership now is a conscious and intentional choice as part of my life as a teacher. I am training future leaders, not only to be the best they can be but also do great things. I am leading them into a fulfilling destination of possibilities. It is clear to me that the benefit of leadership outweighs the cost. Teaching and leading future leaders, inspiring children that they can be what they set their minds and hearts to. Encouraging them to realize their potential at the same time helping them develop new skills and motivate them to get better at what they are doing. I can also be an influencer for good. I lead my students to become better persons who will make better decisions in life. I can lead them to become responsible persons and citizens. As a teacher who leads, I can be a channel of good not only in my school but in the society as well. I am an instrument in making the world a better place.

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